

Genetic Diversity in Indigenous Pig Populations in Humid Forest Agro-Ecological Zone of Nigeria

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Abstract

The relevance of genetic variation study cannot underestimated because it shapes the core for rational decisions on the design of breeding programs and the sustainable use of animal genetic resources. The research was carried out to assess genetic diversity in indigenous pig populations in a humid forest agro-ecological zone of Nigeria using protein markers: hemoglobin (Hb), albumin (Alb), transferrin (Tf) and carbonic anhydrase (Ca). A total of 150 matured pigs with average body weight (40 - 60 kg) were purposively sampled from Ogun, Rivers and Imo States. The fractionation of plasma and red blood cell proteins was determined on cellulose acetate electrophoresis to estimate genetic diversity between populations. The degree of heterozygosity, deviation from Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium (HWE), F_{IS} and F_{ST} values were estimated. Out of a total of 4 loci analyzed, all were found to be polymorphic in all sampled populations. Four co-dominant alleles that control the three genotypes were observed for Alb and Tf while only two alleles were observed for Hb and Ca polymorphic loci. Deviation from Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium and deficiency of heterozygosities were observed in all populations. Deviation from Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium and deficiency of heterozygosities were observed in all populations. Assessment of genetic diversity yielded mean heterozygosity values ranging from 0.375 to 0.686. Heterozygote deficit was quantified with an estimated F_{IT} of 0.108 within the heterozygosity deficit (F_{IS}) of heterozygous species ranging from 0.052 to 0.564. The mean fixation index (F_{ST}) indicates moderate within-population variation ($F_{ST} = 0.018$). Genetic distances calculated using Nei's genetic distance ranged from 0.015 to 0.986, indicating genetic relationships between populations. The result obtained can be used as a preliminary guide to define objectives for future investigation of genetic integrity and development of conservation strategies for Nigeria indigenous pig.

Key words: Pig, Genetic, Albumin, Haemoglobin, Transferrin, Carbonic anhydrate

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Introduction

Nigeria is endowed with an impressive plurality of indigenous livestock, the potential of which cannot be overlooked considering the huge foreign exchange implications of the importation of improved exotic livestock and the genotype-environment interaction that has led to considerable fitness loss of exotic livestock (Fatai *et al.*, 2017). Indigenous animals are valuable both functionally and genetically because they contain genetic materials that can be used for improvement. Knowledge of their genetic diversity is important as it constitutes the basis for designing breeding programs and making rational decisions on the sustainable use of animal genetic resources (Ubu *et al.*, 2021), the selection and development of new breeds with greater resistance to environmental challenges. The loss of genetic diversity within indigenous livestock populations has been a major global concern and the understanding of this has led to efforts to study genetic diversity in livestock species in order to provide a basis for the conservation of these potentially useful germplasms. The loss of genetic variation within and between breeds is detrimental not only from a culture and conservation perspective, but also from a utility perspective, as the lost genes may have economic importance in the future (Ajibike *et al.*, 2020). Within the breed, high rates of genetic variation loss lead to lower chances of breed survival due to lower fitness through inbreeding depression. The genetic characterization of indigenous animals is part of the Food and Agriculture Organization's global strategy for the management of genetic resources of farm animals (FAO, 2024). This strategy places a strong emphasis on the use of molecular methods to aid the conservation of endangered breeds and determine the genetic status of the breeds. These range from electrophoretic detection of polymorphisms of gene products at structural loci to deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) analysis. DNA-based technologies are now the methods of choice for genetic characterization of livestock, however, most diversity and phylogenetic studies are based primarily on microsatellite loci and single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) (Arora *et al.*, 2011). Nigerian indigenous pigs (*Sus scrofa domestica*) are mostly kept under semi-intensive system because of their better adaptation to adverse

climatic conditions of tropical environment and ability to survive under low management inputs (Ubu *et al.*, 2023). Despite their importance, information on the types of blood proteins and or enzymes in Nigerian indigenous pigs is scarce, however, these have been extensively reported in other animal species, especially chicken (Yakubu and Aya, 2012; Ige *et al.*, 2013; Ajayi *et al.*, 2013) and turkey (Fatai *et al.*, 2017; Ubu *et al.*, 2021). Therefore, the present study assessed the genetic diversity of Nigerian indigenous pig populations of the humid forest agro-ecological zone of Nigeria.

Material and Methods

Ethical Approval

There is no ethical approval to this research. All the animals used for the study were under the owner's risk. However, accurate procedures for blood collection and laboratory was appropriately carried out following the guide lines for ethical treatment of animals in applied Animal Behaviour and Warfare Research as prepared by the International Society for Applied Ethology (ISAE) Ethics Committee 2002, and was dully supervised by three Lecturers in the Department of Animal Breeding and Physiology, Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria and two lecturers in the Department of Animal Science (Animal Breeding and Genetics), University of Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Study Location

The study was conducted in the humid forest agro-ecological zone of Nigeria cutting across Ogun State (Latitude 7°0N and Longitude 3°30E), River State (Latitude 4°45' and Longitude N7°0E) and Imo State (Latitude 5°28N and Longitude 7°4E). Humid forest agro-ecological zone of Nigeria has high annual rainfall of 2000 – 4000 mm around August/September, supporting lush vegetation, high humidity of about 78-89 %, and temperatures around 25-28°C, with contrasting climate change (Wikipedia.com). Pigs are predominantly raised in this region using tradition or semi-intensive management practices, and they are known to possess distinctive adaptations suited to this environment. The locations for the study were chosen specifically due to the high prevalence of Nigeria indigenous pigs in these areas.

Map of Nigeria Shown Study Area

Experimental Animals Sampling and their Management

One hundred and fifty (150) matured Nigerian indigenous pigs consisting of 25 males and 25 females of average body weight (40 – 60 kg) in each of the selected States were used for this study. Three (3) States were drawn randomly from a large random mating population of male and female pigs. They were mainly raised by owners under semi-intensive or traditional free range systems; whereby pigs scavenge for their feed and water with little or no supplementation. Only apparently healthy pigs were used for the study.

Blood sample collection from the animals

Approximately 4 ml whole blood was collected from the jugular vein of each of 150 pigs into labeled unheparinized tubes with heparin content and heparinized tubes containing heparin, which acts as an anti-coagulant, and blood contamination was prevented by using separate syringes and needles for each pig. The samples were kept refrigerated in ice packs and transported to the Animal Breeding and Genetics Laboratory of the Department of Animal Sciences, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria for electrophoretic analysis.

Genotyping

Blood samples were centrifuged at 3000 rpm at 4°C for 20 minutes to separate plasma and erythrocytes. Compatibly labeled unheparinized tubes were used for plasma. Erythrocytes were washed with saline drops and centrifuged again for 20 minutes at 3000 rpm, and then lysed with cold distilled water to release haemoglobin.

Plasma and hemolysates aliquots were stored at 4°C prior to electrophoresis analysis. Lysed red blood cells were used to determine haemoglobin and carbonic anhydrase genotypes, while plasma was used to detect albumin and transferrin genotypes.

Electrophoresis polymorphism for proteins (Alb, Hb, Tf) and enzymes (Ca) was performed using cellulose acetate strips. Samples to be electrophoresed were loaded onto the wells using a micropipette and placed on cellulose acetate paper, then placed up and down on wet filter paper across supporters on the bridge from cathode to anode in the electrophoresis machine. Albumin was electrophoresed using Tris citrate buffer at a pH of 8.0, haemoglobin was electrophoresed using Tris borate buffer at a pH of 7.8, transferrin was electrophoresed using Tris glycine at a pH of 6.8, and carbonic anhydrase was electrophoresed using Tris borate at a pH of 7.8.

After electrophoresis, each strip was stained using Coomassie blue for 30 min and then covered with distain solution (1 and 5% acetic acid) until bands were visible, air dried and scored according to RIKEN (2006) and Akinyemi and Salako (2012).

Statistical Analysis

The following were statistically analyzed:

Genotypic and allelic frequency

Genotypic and allelic frequencies for each locus in each sample were calculated by direct counting. Allelic variants were identified for each locus in order of increasing mobility after each electrophoretic run. At all loci, homozygote genotype AA was represented by a

single fast band; the single slow band was designated as BB homozygote, while the presence of both bands (fast and slow bands) was designated as AB heterozygote, respectively. Carbonic anhydrase genotypes were designated as homozygote fast (FF), homozygote (MM) and heterozygote genotypes (FS), respectively.

Genetic variation

Three genetic diversity parameters namely heterozygote (H), effective number of alleles (NE) and percent polymorphism (%P) were used to assess genetic variability in the samples.

The unbiased estimate of mean heterozygosity (Nei, 1972) was estimated as

$$\text{Heterozygosity (H)} = 1 - \sum X_i^2$$

Were:

X = The gene frequency of the allele in a locus
The number of tested loci

The effective number of allele (ne) per locus was estimated as: $1/1-H$

Were:

H = heterozygosity (Nyamsamba *et al.*, 2003).

Polymorphic percentage: A locus is polymorphic if there is more than one segregating gene and the frequency of the rare gene is at least 0.01 % (Sanjalaj *et al.*, 2002). All calculations were performed using the PopGene program (Yeh *et al.*, 1999).

F-statistics

Wright's F-statistics, genetic differentiation (FST), inbreeding coefficient (FIS), and total inbreeding (FIT) were estimated using the Genetic Analysis in Excel (GENAlex) version 6.5 statistical program.

Test for deviation from Hardy–Weinberg equilibrium

A chi-square test (χ^2 test) based on the Hardy–Weinberg law was performed to measure genetic balance at the locus level for each population. The chi-square test was used to evaluate whether loci and populations were in Hardy–Weinberg equilibrium using the Genetic Analysis in Excel (GENAlex) version 6.5 statistical program.

Genetic Distances (DS)

Standardized genetic distances between populations were calculated according to Ney and Hay (1979).

Genetic identity/similarity

The index of similarity was calculated in all possible pair-wise comparisons between lines following the method of Nei and Hi (1979).

Dendrogram

The genetic relatedness of populations was determined by constructing dendrograms using Tools for Population Genetics Analysis (TFPGA), (Miller, 1997).

Results

Genotypic and allelic frequency of four blood protein loci of Nigerian indigenous pig ecotypes

Genotypic frequencies of albumin, haemoglobin, transferrin and carbonic anhydrase are presented in Table 1. Eight distinct genotypes (Alb^{AA}, Alb^{AB}, Alb^{AD}, Alb^{BB}, Alb^{BC}, Alb^{BD}, Alb^{CC} and Alb^{CD}) were observed at the albumin locus with the highest abundance of Alb^{CD} at the albumin locus among the pig ecotypes. The frequency of Alb^{AA} (0.167) was similar for River State and Imo State pig ecotypes. Alb^{AA} and Alb^{CC} had similar frequencies of 0.167 for the Ogun State and River State pig ecotypes, respectively. The similarity in genotypic frequency was same with Alb^{AA} (0.167) and Alb^{BC}, while Alb^{AD} (0.083) had similar frequency with Alb^{BC} and Alb^{CD}, respectively. At the haemoglobin locus, only two genotypes (AA and AB) were observed for all three pig populations with Hb^{AA} (0.583) having the highest overall incidence for all populations studied. Hb^{BB} was not detected in the studied pig population. Eight types of transferrin (Tf^{AA}, Tf^{AC}, Tf^{AD}, Tf^{BB}, Tf^{BC}, Tf^{BD}, Tf^{CC} and Tf^{DD}) were found in the three pig ecotypes, however, Tf^{DD} (0.250) genotype was prevalent in Ogun State pig ecotype, Tf^{BC} (0.500) was dominant in River State pig ecotype while Tf^{AA}, Tf^{AC} and Tf^{BD} had similar frequency of 0.083 in Imo State pig ecotype. Electrophoretic analysis of the carbonic anhydrase locus revealed three different genotypes (Ca^{FF}, Ca^{FS} and Ca^{MM}). However, the genotype Ca^{FF} with overall incidence (0.610) was pervasive among the three ecotypes.

Table 1: Genotypic frequencies of four blood protein loci of Nigerian indigenous pig ecotypes

Locus	Genotype	Ogun State (n=50)	River State (n=50)	Imo State (n=50)	Overall (n=150)
Alb	AA	0.250	0.167	0.167	0.195
	AB	0.500	0.333	0.250	0.361
	AD	0.000	0.083	0.083	0.055
	BB	0.000	0.250	0.083	0.111
	BC	0.000	0.000	0.083	0.028
	BD	0.000	0.000	0.167	0.056
	CC	0.167	0.167	0.083	0.139
	CD	0.083	0.000	0.804	0.055
Hb	AA	0.583	0.667	0.500	0.583
	AB	0.417	0.333	0.500	0.417
	BB	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Tf	AA	0.167	0.083	0.083	0.111
	AC	0.083	0.000	0.083	0.055
	AD	0.000	0.000	0.167	0.056
	BB	0.000	0.083	0.167	0.083
	BC	0.333	0.500	0.333	0.389
	BD	0.167	0.250	0.083	0.167
	CC	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	DD	0.083	0.083	0.084	0.139
Ca	FF	0.500	0.666	0.666	0.139
	FS	0.250	0.167	0.167	0.195
	MM	0.250	0.167	0.167	0.195

Alb = Albumin, Hb = Haemoglobin, Tf = Transferrin, Ca = Carbonic anhydrase

Allelic frequencies at the albumin, haemoglobin, transferrin and carbonic anhydrase loci of the Nigerian indigenous pig ecotype are presented in Table 2. Four albumin alleles were expressed in both three pig ecotypes. AlbA (0.500) was the most prevalent in the Ogun State pig ecotype while AlbB (0.458 and 0.375) was the most prevalent in the Imo State and Rivers State pig ecotypes, respectively. However, the survival of albumin allele D was lowest in the Ogun State pig ecotype, but similar to that of AlbA and AlbC in the Imo State pig ecotype.

Allele A for haemoglobin was most prevalent in both Ogun State (0.792), Rivers State (0.833) and Imo State (0.750) pig ecotypes. At the transferrin locus, allele D (0.334) was most prevalent in the Ogun State pig ecotype, while allele B (0.459) and (0.375) were most prevalent in the Rivers State and Imo State pig ecotypes, respectively. Allele F at the carbonic anhydrase locus was prevalent in all pig ecotypes with frequencies of 0.500, 0.666 and 0.666 for Ogun State, Rivers State and Imo State pig ecotypes, respectively.

Table 2: Allelic frequencies of four blood protein loci of Nigerian indigenous pig ecotypes

Locus	Allelic	Ogun State (n=50)	River State (n=50)	Imo State (n=50)	Overall (n=150)
Alb	A	0.500	0.083	0.208	0.264
	B	0.250	0.458	0.375	0.361
	C	0.208	0.250	0.208	0.222
	D	0.042	0.209	0.208	0.153
Hb	A	0.792	0.833	0.750	0.792
	B	0.208	0.167	0.250	0.208
Tf	A	0.208	0.083	0.208	0.166
	B	0.250	0.459	0.376	1.362

	C	0.208	0.250	0.208	0.222
	D	0.334	0.208	0.208	0.250
Ca	F	0.500	0.666	0.666	0.610
	S	0.250	0.167	0.167	0.195
	M	0.250	0.167	0.167	0.195

Alb = Albumin, Hb = Haemoglobin, Tf = Transferrin, Ca = Carbonic anhydrase

Genetic variability between ecotypes

The results of genetic variability among the ecotypes studied are presented in Table 3. Heterozygosity (H) values of the three ecotypes ranged from 0.410 to 0.458, while the average heterozygosity (H) value was 0.429. The

effective number of alleles (Ne) ranged from 0.962 to 1.264; the average of the three ecotypes is 1.082. All protein-coding loci studied in all three ecotypes were 100 percent polymorphic.

Table 3: Genetic variability of four blood protein loci of Nigerian indigenous pig ecotypes

Locus	Sample Size	Ogun (n=50)	State River (n=50)	State Imo State (n=50)	Mean (150)
Alb	150	0.583	0.417	0.583	0.528
Hb	150	0.222	0.417	0.500	0.380
Tf	150	0.583	0.750	0.667	0.667
Ca	150	0.250	0.083	0.083	0.139
Mean H	150	0.410	0.417	0.458	0.429
Ne		1.264	1.020	0.962	1.082
P(%)		100	100	100	100

Alb = Albumin, Hb = Haemoglobin, Tf = Transferrin, Ca = Carbonic anhydrase, Mean H = Mean Heterozygosity, Ne = Effective Number of Alleles, P(%) = Percentage Polymorphism

Estimated Heterozygosity of Nigerian Indigenous Pig Populations

Table 4 presents the results of heterozygosity in the pooled population and the test of deviation from Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium.

The average heterozygosity ranged from 0.375 to 0.686 and the mean value was 0.543 ± 0.156 . None of the protein loci examined significantly ($P > 0.01$) deviated from Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium.

Table 4: Estimates of heterozygosity for all loci in a pooled population

Locus	Sample size	H _o	H _e	Ave H	HWE	
					Chi-Sq	Prb
Alb	150	0.556	0.684	0.666	4.311	0.230
Hb	150	0.500	0.380	0.375	0.889	0.346
Tf	150	0.722	0.721	0.686	2.091	1.000
Ca	150	0.194	0.457	0.446	0.000	
Mean	150	0.493	0.561	0.543		
SEM		0.220	0.167	0.156		

Alb = Albumin, Hb = Hemoglobin, Tf = Transferrin, Ca = Carbonic Anhydrase, H_o = Observed Heterozygosity, H_e = Expected Heterozygosity, Ave H = Average Heterozygosity, HWE = Hardy Weinberg Equilibrium, Chi-Sq = Chi Square, Prb = Probability.

Genetic diversity in males and females of Nigerian indigenous pig ecotypes

Sex differences in gene and genotype frequencies of Alb, Hb, Tf and Ca of male and female Nigerian indigenous pig ecotypes are presented in Table 5. Of the eight genotypes expressed at the albumin locus (Alb^{AA}, Alb^{AB}, Alb^{AC}, Alb^{AD}, Alb^{BB}, Alb^{CC} and Alb^{CD}), seven were observed in male pigs except Alb^{BC}. In contrast, only five (Alb^{AA}, Alb^{AB}, Alb^{BB}, Alb^{BC} and Alb^{CC}) were observed in female pigs. Furthermore, allele A (0.417) was prevalent in male pigs, while alleles B and C (0.222) had similar frequencies in male pigs and allele A (0.417) had similar frequencies with allele A in female pigs. Two genotypes and two alleles were expressed at the HB locus in the two sexes. The genotypes Hb^{AA} and Hb^{BB} (0.500) were similar

in males while Hb^{AA} was dominant in female pigs. Allele A (0.750 and 0.806) had the highest frequency in both sexes. Six genotypes at the transferrin locus (Tf^{AA}, Tf^{AC}, Tf^{AD}, Tf^{BB}, Tf^{BC} and Tf^{DD}) were observed in male pigs while five genotypes (Tf^{AC}, Tf^{BB}, Tf^{BC}, Tf^{BD} and Tf^{DD}) were expressed in females. Comparative sex-related genotype expression at the transferrin locus revealed that the genotypes Tf^{AA} and Tf^{AD} were found only in males while Tf^{BD} was expressed only in female pigs. Four alleles were expressed in each of both sexes. Alleles B (0.306) and D (0.306) had the highest prevalent frequencies in both sexes. Three different genotypes at the Ca locus (Ca^{FF}, Ca^{FS} and Ca^{MM}) were observed for both sexes. The Ca^{FF} genotype and allele F were prevalent in both male and female pigs.

Table 5: Genes and genotypic frequencies of four blood protein markers in male and female Nigerian indigenous pig ecotypes

Locus	Male				Female			
	Genotype	Obs.	Gene	Freq.	Genotype	Obs.	Gene	Freq.
Alb	AA	0.167	A	0.416	AA	0.222	A	0.417
	AB	0.333	B	0.222	AB	0.389	B	0.417
	AC	0.057	C	0.222	AC	0.000	C	0.166
	AD	0.111	D	0.140	AD	0.000	D	0.000
	BB	0.056			BB	0.167		
	BC	0.000			BC	0.111		
	CC	0.167			CC	0.111		
	CD	0.109			CD	0.000		
Hb	AA	0.500	A	0.750	AA	0.611	A	0.806
	AB	0.500	B	0.250	AB	0.389	B	0.194
	BB	0.000			BB	0.000		
Tf	AA	0.222	A	0.250	AA	0.000	A	0.128
	AC	0.056	B	0.306	AC	0.111	B	0.385
	AD	0.056	C	0.167	AD	0.000	C	0.210
	BB	0.333	D	0.277	BB	0.056	D	0.277
	BC	0.167			BC	0.444		
	BD	0.000			BD	0.222		
	DD	0.166			DD	0.167		
Ca	FF	0.500	F	0.639	FF	0.722	F	0.778
	FS	0.278	S	0.139	FS	0.111	S	0.056
	MM	0.222	M	0.222	MM	0.167	M	0.166

Alb = Albumin, Hb = Haemoglobin, Tf = Transferrin, Ca = Carbonic anhydrase, Obs = Observed, Freq. = Frequency

Table 6 shows the estimated genetic variability of males and females of Nigerian indigenous pig ecotypes. The mean heterozygosity (H) results of the sexes indicated that the predicted value of males was greater than that of females

(0.514 > 0.444). The effective number of alleles (Ne) for male and female pigs was 0.863 and 0.986, respectively. All loci examined were 100 percent polymorphic in both sexes.

Table 6: Estimated genetic variability of male and female Nigerian indigenous pig ecotypes at four blood protein loci

Sex	Total number of Alleles	Heterozygosity				Mean H	Ne	P(%)
		Alb	Hb	Tf	Ca			
Male (75)	7	0.556	0.500	0.723	0.278	0.514	0.863	100
Female (75)	7	0.500	0.389	0.777	0.111	0.444	0.963	100

Alb = Albumin, Hb = Haemoglobin, Tf = Transferrin, Ca = Carbonic anhydrase, Ne = Expect number of alleles, P = Percentage polymorphism

Table 7 presents the results of average heterozygosity in the sampled population. F_{IS} values (0.667) were higher in the Imo State population indicating higher levels of inbreeding. Moderately high values ranging

from 0.637 to 1.309 were reported for the Shannon Information Index. Estimates of heterozygosity for all loci in the collected population and F-statistics and gene flow for all loci studied.

Table 7: Estimating the average heterozygosity in a sampled population

Population	Sample size	H_o	H_e	Ne	I^*	F_{IS}
Ogun State	42	0.667	0.773	3.429	1.309	0.650
River State	56	0.667	0.485	1.800	0.637	0.361
Imo State	52	0.500	0.682	2.667	1.127	0.667

H_o = observed heterozygosity, H_e = expected heterozygosity, Ne = expected number of alleles, I^* = Shannon information index, F_{IS} = fixation index/inbreeding coefficient.

Estimates of heterozygosity and F-statistics for all loci in the pooled population and gene flow for all loci studied

F-statistics and gene flow for all loci studied are presented in Table 8. The estimated heterozygosity deficit (F_{IT}) was 0.108 and the population deficit in heterozygosity assessed by

F_{IS} ranged from 0.052 (Tf) to 0.564 (Ca), with a total of 0.092 for all loci studied. Within population discrimination assessed by F_{ST} was estimated at 0.018 with a range of 0.000 (Hb) to 0.035 (Tf). Gene flow (N_m) values for each of the four loci studied ranged from 0.000 for Hb to 20.625 for Ca. The average gene flow (N_m) over all studied loci was 13.938.

Table 8: F-statistics and gene flow for all loci in the loci studied

Locus	Sample size	F_{IS}	F_{IT}	F_{ST}	N_m^*
Alb	150	0.165	0.176	0.013	18.750
Hb	150	0.333	0.333	0.000	0.000
Tf	150	0.052	0.016	0.035	6.949
Ca	150	0.564	0.569	0.012	20.625
Mean	150	0.092	0.108	0.018	13.938

Alb = albumin, Hb = hemoglobin, Tf = transferrin, Ca = carbonic anhydrase, F_{IS} = inbreeding coefficient, F_{IT} = total inbreeding estimate, F_{ST} = mean difference, N_m^* = gene flow estimated from $F_{ST} = 0.25(1 - F_{ST})/F_{ST}$

Genetic distance between ecotypes

Nei's genetic identity (above the diagonal) and genetic distance (below the diagonal) between the studied ecotypes are presented in Table 9. Further genetic relatedness is presented as a dendrogram in Figure 1.

The Rivers State and Imo State ecotypes lie in the same cluster and are distinct from the Ogun State ecotype.

Table 9: Nei's genetic identity (above diagonal) and genetic distance (below diagonal) among studied ecotypes

Population	Ogun State	River State	Imo State
Ogun State		0.950	0.970
River State	0.051		0.986
Imo State	0.030	0.015	

Fig 1: Dendrogram of genetic distance between three sample populations of Nigeria indigenous pig breeds

Discussion

The observed albumin genotypes (Alb^{AA} , Alb^{AB} , Alb^{AC} , Alb^{AD} , Alb^{BB} , Alb^{BC} , Alb^{BD} , Alb^{CC} , and Alb^{CD}) controlled by the co-dominant alleles A, B, C, and D in this study are consistent with the report of Gao *et al.* (2018) who observed 16 albumin genotypes and 4 alleles in the pig population of China. Chen *et al.* (2017) observed 3 albumin genotypes (Alb^{DD} , Alb^{DE} , and Alb^{EE}) controlled by 2 alleles (D and E) in Chinese pigs. Wang *et al.* (2019) observed 3 albumin genotypes (Alb^{AA} , Alb^{AB} and Alb^{BB}) and 2 alleles (A and B) in pig populations from China and the West using (PCR-RFLP). The variation in the number of genotypes reported in this study and in previous studies could probably be due to the types of molecular techniques used. Since blood protein markers detect a larger number of genotypes than PCR-RFLP. It was observed that the eight genotypes detected in the ecotypes were all present in the pigs of Imo State. This can probably be attributed to differences in ecological pressures and adaptations of pigs to their respective environments. This avowal is consistent with the report by Adediran *et al.* (2019) who found that pig ecotypes from Imo State have higher genetic diversity in albumin genes and

genotypes due to suitable ecological niche. The two haemoglobin genotypes Hb^{AA} and Hb^{AB} controlled by two Hb alleles (A and B) reported in this study are consistent with those reported in Nigerian adapted Duroc pig populations by Nwanchukwu *et al.* (2022). Similar results were reported by Yakubu and Aya (2012), Ajayi *et al.* (2013) and Ige *et al.* (2013) in chickens. The high prevalence of allele HbA observed at the haemoglobin locus in this study is not consistent with the findings of Fatai *et al.* (2017) who reported a high frequency of allele B at this locus in Nigerian domestic turkeys. This may be attributed to species differences or may be due to adaptive significance. Additionally, Ubu *et al.* (2021) reported the dominance of allele HbA at this locus in Nigerian indigenous turkeys. The study also showed that the Hb^{BB} genotype was absent; this may be due to the selective advantage of pigs through evolutionary adaptation to low susceptibility environments, as Hb^{BB} is commonly associated with high-susceptibility adapted species such as cattle, sheep and goats. The transferrin genotypes (Tf^{AA} , Tf^{AC} , Tf^{AD} , Tf^{BB} , Tf^{BC} , Tf^{BD} , Tf^{CC} and Tf^{DD}) and alleles (Tf A, B, C and D) reported in the study are consistent with the report of Zhang *et al.*

(2019) who observed alleles (Tf^{AA}, Tf^{AB}, Tf^{AC}, Tf^{AD}, Tf^{AE}, Tf^{BB}, Tf^{BC}, Tf^{BD}, Tf^{BE}, Tf^{CC}, Tf^{CD} and Tf^{CE}) and alleles (Tf A, B, C, D and E) in Chinese pigs using PCR-RFLP markers. However, the difference in the number of alleles used in the present study and previous studies may be attributed to the effect of molecular markers. Transferrin polymorphism has also been reported in other animal species, such as chicken (Gambo *et al.*, 2020), duck (Oguntunji and Ayorinde, 2015), goat (Salako *et al.*, 2019), sheep (Kilic *et al.*, 2018) and cattle (Liu, 2020). Tf^{BC} and Tf^{BD} are dominant at the transferrin locus. Effect of heterozygous transferrin on fertility has biological functional effects. It has been suggested by Stratil (2019) that heterozygous transfer (Tf^{BC}) influences fertility in pigs. Pigs with homozygous Tf^{AA} genotypes have delayed sexual maturity while pigs with homozygous Tf^{BB} genotypes have an earlier age at sexual maturity (Das and Deb, 2008). The prevalence of allele D and C at the transferrin locus probably indicates the importance of these alleles for pig survival and adaptation in the study area, since transferrin makes iron unavailable to pathogens, thus, inhibiting their cell perferating activities. In this study, three genotypes (Ca^{FF}, Ca^{FS} and Ca^{MM}) driven by two (F and M) alleles expressed at the carbonic anhydrase locus are similar to the report by Wang *et al.* (2020) who reported similar alleles in China pigs. Similarly, allele F is dominant in both ecotypes, consistent with the report of Fatai *et al.* (2017) who observed Ca^{FF}, Ca^{FS} and Ca^{MM} genotypes and two Ca F and Ca M in Nigerian domestic turkeys. In addition, Oguntunji and Ayorinde (2015) reported three alleles at Ca loci for Nigerian Muscovy duck. The study showed that two codominant alleles Ca F and Ca M were observed. However, the frequency of Ca F was consistently higher than M in all populations studied. This is consistent with the report of Ige *et al.* (2013) who observed predominance of Ca F in Yoruba and Fulani ecotype chickens. In contrast, Fatai *et al.* (2017) reported a high frequency of allele Ca S at this locus in Nigerian domestic turkeys. This apparent contradiction between the present study and previous studies may be due to gender differences.

The presence of high Ca^{MM} observed in this study confirms the survival mechanism of pigs, as Ca^{MM} has thermal stability, which allows them to more effectively maintain acid-base balance and electrolyte homeostasis during heat stress (Gao *et al.*, 2020).

The average estimated heterozygosity obtained for the blood proteins in the present study was within the range (0.30 – 0.80) suggested for a marker to be useful in evaluating genetic variation in a population (Takenazi and Nei, 1996). The moderate heterozygosity in the populations under study appears to support the widely held notion that gene pools of locally adapted animals form rich reservoirs of rare genes (Oguntunji and Ayorinde, 2015). The moderate estimate of heterozygosity in a population may be due to the small number of alleles segregating at each locus. No more than four alleles were found to differ at each of the loci studied. Various studies have shown that higher numbers of alleles affect estimated heterozygosity values (Akinyemi and Salako, 2012; Akinyemi *et al.*, 2014; Gambo *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, the small sample size may also be another factor contributing to moderate heterozygosity.

Average heterozygosity (AveH): The average heterozygosity (AveH) reported for the locus under investigation (0.543±0.156) was moderate and relatively high compared to 0.330 to 0.430 reported in the Portuguese pig breeds for microsatellite markers (Santos *et al.*, 2016), 0.350 to 0.350 in the Pini population. (Huang *et al.*, 2012), 0.360 to 0.450 in the French pig breed (Girard *et al.*, 2020) and 0.360 to 0.450 in the Tibetan pig population (Yan *et al.*, 2020), obtained for the studied populations using whole genomic sequencing (WG) markers. The values of heterozygosity point to the fact that there is sufficient genetic variability in the studied population. Genetic diversity observed in studied populations is an important trait of a species/population for adaptation to various environmental challenges. Besides, it is also a veritable tool for the animal breeder in the selection and genetic improvement of farm animals (Oguntunji and Ayorinde, 2015).

Percentage polymorphic loci (% P): The absolute 100% polymorphism at the protein-coding loci investigated in this study is similar to that reported by Pérez-Enciso *et al.* (2017) on Iberian pig breeds. The 100% polymorphic loci observed in this study are an indication of the absence of selection with respect to the loci investigated and restore the diversity widely reported in the genomes of indigenous porcine species in developing countries.

Effective number of alleles (ne): Compared to other indigenous pig breeds, the mean effective number of alleles (1.082) reported in this study is lower than 2.850 reported for Chinese

indigenous pig breeds (Huang *et al.*, 2020) using microsatellite markers. The effective number of alleles (N_e) is an indication of genetic richness of population. Its value is a function of the number of alleles, so in most cases; A greater number of alleles segregating at different loci will produce a greater effective number of alleles and vice versa. The low effective number of alleles observed in this study may indicate a genetic bottleneck effect.

Chi-square analysis: Differences between observed and expected genotype frequencies showed that on the overall data set, only carbonic anhydrase deviated significantly from Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium in all four studied loci, indicating a lack of random mating or dispersive population structuring forces. This observation is similar to that reported by Huang *et al.* (2020) who observed significant variation of carbonic anhydrase in Chinese indigenous pig breeds due to evolutionary forces.

There is scarce information in the literature on the association of sex with blood protein polymorphisms and genetic diversity inferred from blood protein markers in Nigerian indigenous pig breeds to compare or validate the results of the present study. However, the albumin locus is dominated by the A and B genes in both sexes, suggesting the possibility of sex-linked physiological advantages that these genes confer to each sex. However, observed disparities in the distribution of these protein markers deserve confirmation with larger samples and/or studies conducted in controlled environments. Although this result is consistent with the report of Tian *et al.* (2017) who found the prevalence of allele A of albumin gene in both male and female pigs from different pig breeds in India. The haemoglobin locus in the present study showed a high frequency of HbA gene in both male and female pigs which is in agreement with the reports of Liu *et al.* (2017) on male and female Chinese pigs and Gao *et al.* (2018) in different pig breeds but in contrast to the report of Tian *et al.* (2017) in different breeds of pigs where the HbB gene was dominant in males and females. The high frequency of HbA in the two breeds of Nigerian indigenous pigs studied indicates the absence of sex influence on its expression. The transferrin locus showed the prevalence of genotypes Tf^{BB} and Tf^{BC} in the two breeds and was associated with a high frequency of gene TfB which is a clear indication of the importance of the gene in the population under study. In addition, the similarity in the distribution of genes in the two sexes suggests that sex has

no influence on the expression of transferrin genotypes and alleles. The report of this study is consistent with the report of Liu *et al.* (2018) and Wang *et al.* (2020) on Chinese pig breeds. The mean heterozygosity in each of the two breeds falling within the required range (0.3 - 0.8) for the breed to qualify for genetic improvement indicates the allelic richness and diversity of this population. In addition, the estimated heterozygosity for male and female pigs in this study was higher than the values reported for males (0.342) and females (0.377) in Chinese pigs (Chen *et al.*, 2019). The high average heterozygosity in this study and previous studies can be attributed to intense selection for desirable traits.

Males have a lower effective number of alleles (N_e) than females. This could possibly be attributed to the attendant effect of high female heterozygosity. The effective number of alleles in this study agrees with Zhang *et al.* (2019) in Chinese pig breeds but in contrast to the report of Oguntunji and Ayorinde (2015) on Muscovy ducks. The variation may be due to gender differences. The percentage of polymorphic loci showed that all loci examined were polymorphic and this agreed with a similar study on both domestic pig breeds in Africa using mitochondrial DNA markers (Okoye *et al.*, 2019).

Heterozygosity deficit (F_{IT}) and within breed deficit in heterozygosity assessed by F_{IS} ranged from 0.01 to 0.15 - reported by Diez *et al.* (2017) in Spanish domestic pigs. Within species variation assessed by F_{ST} ranged from 0.05 to 0.30 reported by Zhang *et al.* (2018) in Chinese commercial pigs. Gene flow values for each of the four loci reported by Gao *et al.* (2019) ranged from 0.40 to 0.50 in Chinese commercial pigs. The observed heterozygous deficit obtained in this study is an indication that they were under the same evolutionary forces. Wright's (1978) fixation index (F_{ST}) value observed ranged from 0.0000 to 0.035 indicating that the genetic diversity among the populations studied was moderately different (Cavalli-Sforza *et al.*, 1981). Observation of positive and low values of F_{ST} and F_{IT} indicated deficiency of heterozygotes in the population. This may be a trait effect of genetic drift.

The genetic distance between the studied populations was higher than the range of 0.000 and 0.058 reported by Nei (1976) for local species. Distance represents the variation between studied populations; the populations of Imo State and Rivers State cluster together above the population of Ogun State (Fig. 1).

Conclusion

From the results obtained in this study, it can be concluded that the similarity in the frequencies of genotypes and alleles in the three investigated populations indicates that they are under the same evolutionary trends. The values of genetic diversity parameters estimated for pigs in this study show that the three ecotypes are variable in their genomes and there are possibilities of genetic improvement if crossed with exotic or pigs from other populations not covered in this study. Carbonic anhydrase loci deviation in Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium are due to population migration. The variability observed in Nigerian indigenous pig populations can serve as a boost for their conservation and sustainable Nigerian indigenous pig ecotypes genetic resources. The genetic variability observed in this study emphasizes the potential for conserving and sustainably utilizing Nigerian indigenous pig ecotypes, ensuring the preservation of their unique genetic resources for future biotechnological applications and breeding programs.

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